

Slash and Burn as a Traditional Agroforestry Culture in Finland

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Forest being prepared for slash and burn in Koli National Park in Eastern Finland (Photo: Tanja Kähkönen)

In Finland, slash and burn agriculture has been a traditional agroforestry practice. The aim of the slash and burn agriculture was to be able to produce crops on burnt forest land. Slash and burn is an example of sequential agroforestry in which trees and crops are grown in the same land area in temporal sequence, in this case first trees and after it crops.

The stages of slash and burn include drying trees, cutting trees and burning trees in the slash and burn area. After burning, ashes are spread evenly to the burnt area, soil is prepared for cultivation, and seeding of the area with crops is done. Traditionally rye and turnip were used as crops in slash and burn agriculture. Each area was used for crop production typically 2 to 3 years, and up to 5 years, after burning the forest. After this, the area was let to become forest again and/or it was used as pasture for animals. Slash and burn agriculture notably decreased at the end of the 19th century when different valuable uses for wood were developed with the last slash and burn being burnt in Koli in Eastern Finland at the beginning of the 20th century.

In Koli National Park in Eastern Finland, slash and burn has been practiced again since 1994 as a measure for maintaining cultural heritage and as a measure for nature management. Volunteers have been typically invited to participate in annual preparation and burning of slash and burn. Planted forests are primarily used in slash and burn to restore forest to natural condition through burning. Besides creating habitats for species dependent on fire, slash and burn also helps to maintain the genetic pool of traditional slash and burn rye and turnip seeds in Finland.

In Koli National Park, slash and burn areas are grazed by sheep. Combining traditional practice of slash burn with preservation and management of traditional rural landscapes has opened possibilities of creating new business opportunities - the herder holiday as an agroforestry voluntourism concept.

References

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